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Assessing Livelihood Vulnerability Using a Composite Index in Communities Surrounding Riverine Wildlife Sanctuaries of Assam, India

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Abstract

Objectives: The purpose of the present research is to assess the livelihood vulnerability of flood-affected communities residing in the fringe villages of riverine wildlife sanctuaries in Assam using a comprehensive, index-based evaluation framework. **Methods:** The Livelihood Vulnerability Index (LVI) was calculated using a balanced weighted average method that included institutional, environmental, and socioeconomic factors. Based on the different levels of flood susceptibility, the research region was separated into three distinct flood-prone belts to allow for a more thorough investigation of vulnerability. Two representative villages were purposefully chosen for in-depth field surveys from each of these belts to ensure balanced spatial coverage. Primary data were collected through household surveys, employing a random sampling technique. A total of 264 households (constituting approximately 30% of the total 880 households) were surveyed. Geospatial analysis supported exposure assessment. Adaptive capacity and sensitivity were evaluated using indicator-based scoring, and inter-village comparisons were performed to identify vulnerability gradients and gaps in resilience. **Findings:** The study reveals high livelihood vulnerability in the fringe villages of Assam's riverine wildlife sanctuaries, primarily due to frequent flooding, erosion, and inadequate institutional support. The calculated Livelihood Vulnerability Index (LVI) across six villages (3 belts) ranges from 0.349 in Belt 3 (indicating lower vulnerability) to 0.438 in Belt 1 (highest vulnerability), with a moderate LVI of 0.374 in Belt 2 of the study area. Communities dependent on agriculture and fishing experience recurring income disruption and food insecurity. The factor of Housing Security and Access to Livelihood Assets shows the greatest vulnerability ratings across the evaluated dimensions, scoring 0.740 in Belt 1, 0.580 in Belt 2, and 0.507 in Belt 3, indicating significant exposure and sensitivity to flood-related risks in these zones. The composite food vulnerability index follows up with scores 0.488, 0.428, and 0.378 for the respective villages present in three belts, indicating a higher level of food-related stress. Comparative analysis shows variability in resilience linked to social capital and access to institutional support.

The results contribute to refining adaptation planning in eco-sensitive flood-prone zones and provide a replicable framework for vulnerability analysis in similar riverine contexts globally. **Novelty:** This study integrates LVI with geospatial exposure mapping to assess livelihood vulnerability in ecologically sensitive flood-prone areas, offering a replicable model for localized, community-level resilience planning.

Keywords: Livelihood Vulnerability Index (LVI); Weighted Average Method (WAM); Flood Risk Assessment; Adaptive Capacity; Disaster Resilience

1 Introduction

Flooding is viewed as a major natural threat that leads to widespread human distress and substantial asset loss frequently around the globe⁽¹⁾. In 2020, the EM-DAT international disaster database documented 389 environmental disasters, resulting in 15,080 fatalities, impacting 98.4 million individuals, and causing economic losses exceeding USD 171.3 billion⁽²⁾. In fact, between 2000 and 2019 Floods accounted for the highest proportion of recorded global disasters & over the same period it was recorded as the second most significant natural disaster in terms of the total number of affected individuals⁽³⁾. According to the Rastriya Barh Ayog(RBA)the flood prone area of Assam is 9.40% of the total flood prone area of the country⁽⁴⁾.

The Brahmaputra floodplain in Assam, like other large alluvial river floodplains, is a dynamic and ecologically significant area that is home to a diverse range of plant, animal, and human species⁽⁵⁾. The Brahmaputra River, which runs along the northern periphery of Laokhowa-Burhachapori Wildlife Sanctuary, has a gradual incline that diminishes its hydraulic efficiency, resulting in silt accumulation on the riverbed⁽⁶⁾. This process contributes to the formation of multiple lateral and mid-channel bars and islands locally referred to as **chars** and **chaporis**, shaping the river's braided morphology⁽⁷⁾. The river's rapid channel bifurcation and shallow bottom limit its ability to hold water. As a result, every year during the monsoon season, when the discharge is high, it frequently exceeds its banks, disrupting local life and causing numerous floods. Recurrent flooding poses a severe threat to stability, particularly in vulnerable regions, by triggering displacement and involuntary migration, intensifying competition over limited resources among native and migrant populations. This, in turn, fosters ethnic tensions, social distrust, political instability, and the potential for civil unrest within the basin⁽⁸⁾.

Livelihood Vulnerability Index (LVI) has been widely employed to assess community vulnerability to a broad spectrum of environmental and socio-economic challenges such as vulnerability due to flood, Climate Change Vulnerability, Drought Vulnerability, Food Security and Agricultural Vulnerability, Economic and Social Vulnerability. Several studies have employed the LVI to assess the vulnerability across various environmental, social, and economic challenges⁽⁹⁾. Building upon these studies, the present research employs the Weighted Average Method (WAM) to compute the LVI, ensuring a more structured and data-driven assessment. The WAM approach is more relevant for regions like the Brahmaputra floodplains, where vulnerability patterns are shaped by complex and localized factors such as seasonal flooding, riverbank erosion, access to natural resources, and socio-economic disparities. Extensive research efforts have been undertaken by numerous scholars to explore this domain in comparable floodplain regions⁽¹⁰⁾. The reviewed literature indicated that, despite the increasing application of the LVI in comparable floodplain regions, its use particularly through the (WAM) remains limited in the context of the Brahmaputra floodplains. Recognizing this gap, the present study aims to contribute meaningful insights by applying this method in fringe villages of the Laokhowa-Burhachapori Wildlife Sanctuary. In the realm of flood-sensitive border villages of LBWS, vulnerability doesn't align with the established categories of exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity, unlike the framework based on IPCC.

2 Methodology

2.1 Study Area

The present study focuses on the vulnerable fringe communities and settlements surrounding two contiguous protected areas (PAs), the Laokhowa Wildlife Sanctuary (LWLS) and the Burhachapori Wildlife Sanctuary (BWLS), situated in the Nagaon and Sonitpur districts of Assam. For the purpose of field investigation, a 6-kilometre buffer zone around the LBWLS was delineated, within which 34 revenue villages were identified. In addition, the Laokhowa WLS comprises seven Taungiya Villages (TVs) and one Forest Village (FV), which was also included in the assessment. Based on the varying levels of flood susceptibility, the study area has been categorized into three distinct flood prone belts to facilitate a more nuanced analysis of vulnerability. From each of these belts, two representative villages were purposively selected for detailed field surveys, ensuring balanced spatial coverage. The details of the case study area villages are presented in Table 1.

Along the northern edge of the BWLS, the riparian belt consists of low-lying, flood-prone territories that stretches up to the Dhania Range Office in the Sonitpur district. For the purposes of this study, two villages—Dhania and Sishuhati, were selected from this belt to represent the characteristic socio-economic and environmental vulnerabilities prevalent in the riparian zone. A stream that runs between the LWLS and BWLS, marks the district boundary of Nagaon and Sonitpur, splits the region into two separate areas and is referred to as the intermediate belt.

Two villages, Bogamukh no.4 and Bogamukh no.5, were selected from this belt to represent the socio-cultural and economic complexities influencing vulnerability among fringe communities. The forest and Taungiya villages, located between the flood control embankment constructed during 1960–1966 and the southern boundary of the LWLS, constitute the peripheral belt. Two villages, Salpara FV and Sutirpar TV, were purposively selected from this belt to reflect the unique vulnerabilities faced by forest-dependent communities. Figure no. 1 provides a detailed representation of the study area.

Fig 1. Location of the study villages

2.2 Sample size and sampling technique

The field investigation was carried out in two distinct phases. The first stage, a reconnaissance survey, was conducted in early October 2023. The second phase, carried out in December 2023, involved comprehensive community engagement and consultations with key stakeholders to collect both primary and secondary data required for the assessment. Primary data were collected through household surveys, employing a random sampling technique. A total of 264 households (constituting approximately 30% of the total 880 households) were surveyed. This sampling approach enabled a robust comparative analysis of the LVI across fringe communities and settlements located in flood-prone zones adjacent to the LWLS and the BWLS.

2.3 Data and Information

Given the study area’s multifaceted nature of livelihood vulnerability influenced by elements like ethnicity, occupation, gender, and availability of institutional support, the use of qualitative methods provided the adaptability to investigate various viewpoints collectively Five Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) were conducted across the selected study areas. Members of local Disaster Risk Management (DRM) Committees, household heads, village leaders, and village heads were among the important stakeholders with whom 15 Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) and a number of in-depth personal interviews were conducted. The applications of such qualitative tools were also valuable in triangulating the quantitative findings and contextualizing the vulnerability profiles of fringe villages located along the dynamic Brahmaputra floodplain⁽¹¹⁾. Participants included farmers, educators, government representatives, healthcare workers, housewives, and students, thereby reflecting a broad cross-section of the community. Secondary data were sourced from a wide range of repositories, including publications by the Central Bureau of Statistics, academic research studies, peer-reviewed journal articles, national policy documents, and official records from municipal and rural municipality offices. Supplementary sources, such as resource maps and GIS datasets, were also utilized to support spatial and thematic analyses.

2.3.1. Calculation of the LVI using a balanced weighted average method

The vulnerability framework, grounded in the IPCC definition⁽¹²⁾ serves as a robust analytical tool for assessing vulnerability. Within this broader framework, an indicator-based vulnerability assessment methodology has since been widely applied by various scholars across diverse contexts⁽¹³⁾. This methodology, known as the Livelihood Vulnerability Index (LVI), was formulated as a composite measure encompassing major components and sub-components. In this study, the methodology proposed by earlier scholars⁽¹³⁾,⁽¹⁴⁾ and applied further by various others⁽¹⁵⁾ was employed to evaluate the vulnerability levels in flood-affected fringe villages of BLWLS. Modifications were made to the methodology to suit the specific context of our case study. In our analysis, two major components, housing and production means (HPM) and natural disaster (ND)⁽¹⁶⁾, were incorporated alongside the six components of the LVI. Table 2 presents all eight major components and 38 sub-components or indicators of livelihood vulnerability utilized in calculating the LVI. The major components of this study were socio-demographic profile (SDP), livelihood strategies (LS), social networks (SN), health (H), food (F), water (W), housing and production means (HPM), natural disasters (ND). Since each sub-component was measured on a different scale, standardization was essential for comparability, and the LVI employs a simple approach by assigning equal weights to all major components. The equation used in Human Development Index methodology to calculate the life expectancy index, which represents the ratio of the difference between actual life expectancy and a predefined minimum value to the range between predetermined maximum and minimum life expectancy⁽¹⁷⁾ as applied which was expressed as **Eq. (1)**.

$$\text{Index}_{sc} = \frac{sc - sc_{\min}}{sc_{\max} - sc_{\min}} \tag{1}$$

Here, Index_{sc} = standardized value of each indicator or sub-component, sc = original or actual value of the sub-component, sc_{\min} = minimum value of each sub-component, and sc_{\max} = maximum value of each sub-component.

Following the standardization of each sub-component, the value of each major component was determined by computing the average of its n sub-components using **Eq. (2)**.

$$M_i = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \text{index } S_i}{n} \tag{2}$$

Here, M_i = One of the eight major components, S_i = Subcomponents indexed by i , n = number of subcomponents in each major component.

Once the values for each of the eight major components for each belt were calculated, LVI was obtained by averaging all major components in each belt using **Eq. (3)**:

$$LVI = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n W_{m_i} M_i}{\sum_{i=1}^8 W_{m_i}} \tag{3}$$

Here, LVI = Livelihood Vulnerability Index. W_{m_i} = Weights of each major components. M_i = each major component.

Equation (3) was further expressed as

$$LVI_d = \frac{W_{SDP}SDP + W_{LS}LS + W_{SN}SN + W_HH + W_FF + W_WW + W_{HPM}HPM + W_{ND}ND}{W_{SDP} + W_{LS} + W_{SN} + W_H + W_F + W_W + W_{HPM} + W_{ND}} \tag{4}$$

Table 1. Details of the case study villages

Study Section	Selected Villages	Latitudinal extension	Longitudinal extension	Community development (CD) Block	Distance from Brahmaputra (in kms)	Flood frequency (last 10 years average)	Households number	Total Households number	Total sample size
Riparian Belt	Dhania	26°32'02"N to 26°32'57"N	92°45'49"E to 92°45'53"E	Gabharu	2	7	153	213	46
	Sishuhati	26°32'58"N to 26°33'01"N	92°45'34"E to 92°45'54"E	Gabharu	1	8	60		18
Intermediate Belt	Bogamukh No.4	26°31'57"N to 26°32'07"N	92°45'44"E to 92°46'12"E	Laokhowa	3	5	227	408	68
	Bogamukh No.5	26°31'01"N to 26°31'57"N	92°45'33"E to 92°46'02"E	Laokhowa	3.7	4	181		54
Peripheral Belt	Salpara FV	26°29'07"N to 26°30'57"N	92°46'06"E to 92°47'27"E	Laokhowa	5.5	4	176	259	53
	Sutirpar TV	26°29'43"N to 26°30'03"N	92°37'29"E to 92°38'32"E	Juria	5.3	6	83		25

Source: Compiled by the authors, 2023

2.3.2. Data Processing and statistical analysis

The data obtained from household surveys, FGDs, and KIIs were initially refined and verified for consistency and completeness. For preliminary data entry, coding, and descriptive statistical analysis Microsoft Excel was utilized. Categorical and continuous variables were methodically coded to correspond with the indicators chosen for calculating the LVI. The results were visualized collectively in a spider diagram which spatially depicted the vulnerability levels across the study area.

3 Results and Discussion

The actual, minimum, and maximum values of each sub-component used in calculating the Livelihood Vulnerability Index (LVI) are summarized in Table 3 and Table 4. The standardized scores of all sub-components, the computed values for each major component, and the overall LVI scores for the study area are presented in Table 5 and Table 6. Additionally, a visual representation of the contribution of each major component to the overall LVI is illustrated through a spider diagram (Figure 2), which helps in identifying the most influential factors contributing to household vulnerability across the surveyed villages.

Table 2. Major components and sub-components comprising the livelihood vulnerability index (LVI)

Major Component	Sub-component	units
Socio-demographic factor	Dependency ratio	Ratio
	Average number of family members in the household	Count
	Percentage of female-headed households	Percent
	Percentage of households headed by someone who has not attended school	Percent
	The household's literacy rate	Percent
	Depending on agriculture as a major source of income	Percent
Livelihood Strategy	The household's nonfarm activities are affected by floods or natural disasters	Percent
	Percentage of households whose head or any other member has the training to cope with flood hazard and other natural disasters	Percent

Continued on next page

Table 2 continued

	Average agricultural livelihood diversification index (range: 0.20–1)	1/livelihoods
	Percentage of households with a family member working in a different community	Percent
Social networks	HHs having job opportunities during the flood season	Percent
	Percentage of households that fished during the flood season	Percent
	Average borrow:lend money ratio (range:0.5–2)	Ratio
	HHs that have gone to the government for assistance in the last 12 months	Percent
	HHs that have generally been treated by a qualified doctor (MBBS doctor)	Percent
Health	Average time to available health facility(minutes)	Minutes
	HHs whose family members have a chronic illness	Percent
	HHs receiving treatment from a local doctor during illness	Percent
	HHs having a sanitary latrine	Percent
	HHs with a family member missing work due to illness in the past two weeks	Percent
Food	Average number of months with insufficient food	Months
	HHs that obtain their food primarily from their own farms	Percent
	Average crop diversity index (range:0–1)	1/crops
	Worried about lack of sufficient food during the last three months	Percent
	HHs that do not save seeds	Percent
Water	HHs practicing homestead gardening	Percent
	HHs reporting water conflicts within their community	Percent
	HHs that use a natural or unsafe water source	Percent
	Average time to get to a safe drinking water source	Minutes
	HHs that easily obtain water from their own source(tubewell)	Percent
Housing and production means	HHs without a solid house	Percent
	HHs with house affected by floods	Percent
	HHs without access to production means	Percent
Natural Disaster	Average number of flood events in the past 10 years	Count
	HHs with an injury or death as a result of a natural disaster in the last 10 years	Percent
	Average number of embankment breaches in the past 10 years	Count
	HHs that do not receive a warning before a natural disaster (flash flood, hailstorm, embankment breach)	Percent
	Average number of months that land was waterlogged	Months

Table 3. Actual, maximum, and minimum values of livelihood vulnerability indices (LVI) for sub-components as stated by Hahn

Major Component	Sub-component	units	Riparian Belt (B1)	Intermediate belt (B2)	Peripheral belt (B3)	Maximum value among all belts	minimum value among all belts
Socio-demographic factor	Dependency ratio	Ratio	1.675	0.786	1.409	3	0
	Average number of family members in the household	Count	4.28	6.1	4.95	14	0
	Percentage of female-headed households	percent	34	16	6.35	100	0
	percentage of households headed by someone who has not attended school	percent	21.9	56.25	37.5	100	0
	The household's literacy rate	percent	53.54	31.2	45.28	100	0

Continued on next page

Table 3 continued

Livelihood Strategy	Depending on agriculture as a major source of income	percent	76.5	90.5	80.4	100	0
	The household's nonfarm activities are affected by floods or natural disasters	percent	82.5	52.5	30.5	100	0
	percentage of households whose head or any other member has the training to cope with flood hazard and other natural disasters	percent	6.5	6	8.5	100	0
	Average agricultural livelihood diversification index (range: 0.20–1)	1/livelihoods	0.29	0.24	0.26	1	0.2
	percentage of households with a family member working in a different community	percent	11	18.5	12.6	100	0
	HHs having job opportunities during the flood season	percent	16	21	13	100	0
	percentage of households that fished during the flood season	percent	29.5	49	32	100	0
Social network	Average borrow:lend money ratio (range:0.5–2)	Ratio	0.657	1.233	1.045	2	0.5
	HHs that have gone to the government for assistance in the last 12 months	percent	51	43.7	37.5	100	0
	HHs that have generally been treated by a qualified doctor (MBBS doctor)	percent	21.5	25.5	20.5	100	0
Health	Average time to available health facility(minutes)	Minutes	53	37.5	53	120	30
	HHs whose family members have a chronic illness	percent	7.5	10	4	100	0
	HHs receiving treatment from a local doctor during illness	percent	76	83.5	79.5	100	0
	HHs having a sanitary latrine	percent	72	66.5	88	100	0
	HHs with a family member missing work due to illness in the past two weeks	percent	10.4	8.5	9.7	100	0
Food	Average number of months with insufficient food	Months	2.49	0.94	0.95	6	0
	HHs that obtain their food primarily from their own farms	percent	45.5	83.6	72.5	100	0
	Average crop diversity index (range:0–1)	1/crops	0.27	0.19	0.19	1	0
	Worried about lack of sufficient food during the last three months	percent	90.5	65.5	55	100	0
	HHs that do not save seeds	percent	68	37.5	25	100	0
	HHs practicing homestead gardening	percent	20	35.5	39.5	100	0

Continued on next page

Table 3 continued

Water	HHs reporting water conflicts within their community	percent	20.5	15.6	11	100	0
	HHs that use a natural or unsafe water source	percent	43.5	34	26	100	0
	Average time to get to a safe drinking water source	Minutes	3.4	4.8	7.2	45	0
	HHs that easily obtain water from their own source (tube well)	percent	56.5	66	74	100	0

Table 4. Actual, maximum, and minimum values of livelihood vulnerability indices (LVI) for sub-components as stated by Sarker

Major Component	Sub-component	units	Riparian Belt (B1)	Intermediate belt (B2)	Peripheral belt (B3)	Maximum value among all belts	minimum value among all belts
Housing and production means	HHs without a solid house	%	91	77	70.5	100	0
	HHs with house affected by floods	%	88	63	59.5	100	0
	HHs without access to production means	%	43	34	22	100	0
	Average number of flood events in the past 10 years	Count	7.5	4.5	5	10	4
Natural Disaster	HHs with an injury or death as a result of a natural disaster in the last 10 years	%	26.5	12.5	10	100	0
	Average number of embankment breaches in the past 10 years	Count	4.5	2.5	4	6	0
	HHs that do not receive a warning before a natural disaster (flash flood, hailstorm, embankment breach)	%	90	81	69	100	0
	Average number of months that land was waterlogged	Month	6.5	3.5	3	8	3

Source: calculated by author, 2024

3.1 Spatial Variation in Livelihood Vulnerability across Flood-Prone Belts

The Livelihood Vulnerability Index (LVI) for peripheral communities in three flood-prone belts encircling the Laokhowa-Burhachapori Wildlife Sanctuary (LBWLS) was computed and the findings show considerable differences in susceptibility by location. The most susceptible is Belt 1, which has the highest LVI score (0.438). Flood effects are more regular and severe because of its near proximity to the Brahmaputra River. Belt 2’s modest LVI of 0.374 indicates comparatively less exposure but ongoing issues with infrastructure, service accessibility, and income stability. Belt 3, with the lowest LVI of 0.349, appears more resilient—likely due to better livelihood diversification, improved service access, and stronger community networks. Nonetheless, the vulnerability level remains significant, underscoring the need for ongoing development support. The next section offers a component-wise breakdown to highlight specific drivers of risk.

3.2 Component-wise Analysis of Vulnerability

The major components within the LVI framework represent key dimensions of livelihood sensitivity, including demographic structure, health, institutional access, and exposure to natural hazards. By breaking down the LVI ratings, the three flood-prone belts’ distinct determinants of vulnerability are shown to vary spatially. This component-level analysis enables a more in depth understanding of the socio-economic and environmental stressors that influence the adaptive capacity of local communities.

3.2.1. Socio-Demographic Determinants of Livelihood Vulnerability

Because household-level factors affect different abilities to prepare for, respond to, and recover from flooding, the socio-demographic factors of livelihood vulnerability exhibit notable geographic differences across the three flood-prone regions.

Table 5 indicates that Belt 1 had the highest composite score for socio demographic risk (0.392), followed by Belts 2 and 3 (0.347 and 0.343, respectively). This suggests that, in relation to the other belts, households in Belt 1 are comparatively more susceptible in terms of socio demographic characteristics. The results show that socio demographic disadvantages increase vulnerability by reducing the ability to absorb and adjust in flood-prone areas.

The overall Livelihood Vulnerability Index (LVI) is calculated to be, Belt 1=0.438, Belt 2=0.374 and Belt 3=0.349

3.2.2. *Livelihood Diversification and Economic Resilience*

The dimension of economic resilience and livelihood diversification assesses the significance of these elements in influencing household vulnerability, particularly in flood-prone rural regions, where they often lead to unstable income sources. As shown in Table 5 and 6, the composite score for this component is highest in Belt 2 (0.346), followed closely by Belt 1 (0.333), with Belt 3 scoring the lowest (0.264). After analyzing the findings it is found that while Belt 2 exhibits relatively higher economic diversification, all three belts share core structural vulnerabilities. Limited livelihood alternatives, negligible access to formal training, weak institutional support for non-farm enterprises, and a high reliance on climate-sensitive income sources collectively hinder household capacity to recover from flood shocks.

3.2.3. *Social Capital and Adaptive Coping Mechanisms*

The component Social Capital and Adaptive Coping Mechanisms examines the extent to which households are embedded in support networks and their ability to seek institutional assistance in times of distress. Belt-wise analysis shows that Belt 2 exhibits the highest index value (0.463), followed by Belt 3 (0.369), while Belt 1 remains the most vulnerable with the lowest score (0.308). Taking together all the indicators it can be stated that social capital, both in terms of reciprocal community networks and institutional engagement plays a pivotal role in shaping a household's resilience. Communities with weak interpersonal ties and over-reliance on government aid are less equipped to take the immediate and long-term shocks of flooding events. Hence, the lack of robust social support mechanisms in Belt 1 amplifies their vulnerability and impedes sustainable recovery.

3.2.4. *Healthcare Accessibility and Disease Exposure*

The component Healthcare Accessibility and Disease Exposure reflects the multifaceted health-related vulnerabilities of households living in the flood-affected fringe villages of LBWLS. As seen in Table 5&6, the overall normalized vulnerability scores for this component range from 0.337 to 0.379 across the surveyed villages, indicating a moderate level of health-related vulnerability. These different indicators illustrate how health vulnerabilities intersect with socio-economic fragility in flood-prone areas. Villages with higher dependency on unqualified medical care and greater distances to health services are less equipped to mitigate the health impacts of recurrent floods. The limited access to qualified treatment, compounded by chronic disease burden and compromised mobility during disasters, amplifies household vulnerability by diminishing coping capacity.

3.2.5. *Food Security and Agro-Resilience*

The component Food Security and Agro-Resilience reflects the multifaceted impact of food access, production stability, and adaptive agricultural practices on household vulnerability in flood-affected fringe villages. As seen in Table 5, the composite food vulnerability index scores are 0.488, 0.428, and 0.378 for the respective villages present in three belts, indicating a relatively higher level of food-related stress compared to other components. In total, the indicators under Food Security and Agro-Resilience not only highlight limited access and exposure to food insecurity but also signal structural weaknesses in agricultural adaptability and institutional support. This increases the sensitivity and decreases the adaptive capacity of the local communities to flood events. Thus, alongside healthcare inaccessibility and disease exposure (as discussed in section 3.2.4), food insecurity forms a critical axis of vulnerability, directly impacting nutritional status, health, and the capacity to recover from recurring floods.

3.2.6. *Water Security and Access*

Water security is a critical determinant of vulnerability in flood-prone fringe villages, especially in regions where drinking water sources are limited or compromised during inundation periods. The water component, comprising indicators such as household (HH) reporting of water conflicts, usage of unsafe water sources, travel time to access safe water, and ease of obtaining water from own sources (Table 5), reflects varying degrees of vulnerability across the study villages. The composite index values were relatively close, 0.320, 0.316, and 0.318 for Belt 1, Belt 2, and Belt 3 respectively, indicating uniformly moderate water-related vulnerability. The findings suggest that water insecurity significantly exacerbates overall livelihood vulnerability. The dependence on unsafe sources, coupled with limited mobility during floods and sporadic maintenance of water infrastructure, limits community resilience.

Table 5. Livelihood vulnerability indices (LVI) for major components and normalized sub-components as per Hahn

Major component	Value of the major components			Sub-components	Standardized value of the subcomponents		
	Belt 1	Belt 1	Belt 2		Belt 1	Belt 2	Belt 3
Socio-demographic factor	0.392	0.347	0.343	Dependency ratio	0.558	0.262	0.47
				Average number of family members in the household	0.306	0.436	0.354
				% age of female-headed households	0.34	0.16	0.064
				% age of households headed by someone who has not attended school	0.219	0.563	0.375
				The household's literacy rate	0.535	0.312	0.453
Livelihood Strategy	0.333	0.346	0.264	Depending on agriculture as a major source of income	0.765	0.905	0.804
				The household's nonfarm activities are affected by floods or natural disasters	0.825	0.525	0.305
				% age of households whose head or any other member has the training to cope with flood hazard and other natural disasters	0.065	0.06	0.085
				Average agricultural livelihood diversification index (range: 0.20–1)	0.113	0.05	0.075
				%age of households with a family member working in a different community	0.11	0.185	0.126
Social networks	0.308	0.463	0.369	HHs having job opportunities during the flood season	0.16	0.21	0.13
				%age of households that fished during the flood season	0.295	0.49	0.32
				Average borrow:lend money ratio (range:0.5–2)	0.105	0.489	0.363
				HHs that have gone to the government for assistance in the last 12 months	0.51	0.437	0.375
				HHs that have generally been treated by a qualified doctor (MBBS doctor)	0.215	0.255	0.205
Health	0.355	0.337	0.379	Average time to available health facility (minutes)	0.256	0.083	0.256
				HHs whose family members have a chronic illness	0.075	0.1	0.04
				HHs receiving treatment from a local doctor during illness	0.76	0.835	0.795
				HHs having a sanitary latrine	0.72	0.665	0.88
				HHs with a family member missing work due to illness in the past two weeks	0.104	0.085	0.097
Food	0.488	0.428	0.378	Average number of months with insufficient food	0.415	0.157	0.158
				HHs that obtain their food primarily from their own farms	0.455	0.836	0.725
				Average crop diversity index (range:0–1)	0.27	0.19	0.19
				Worried about lack of sufficient food during the last three months	0.905	0.655	0.55
				HHs that do not save seeds	0.68	0.375	0.25
Water	0.320	0.316	0.318	HHs practicing homestead gardening	0.2	0.355	0.395
				HHs reporting water conflicts within their community	0.205	0.156	0.11
				HHs that use a natural or unsafe water source	0.435	0.34	0.26
				Average time to get to a safe drinking water source	0.076	0.107	0.16
				HHs that easily obtain water from their own source (tube well)	0.565	0.66	0.74

Table 6. Livelihood vulnerability indices (LVI) for major components and normalized sub-components as per Sarker

Major component	Value of the major components			Sub-components	Standardized value of the subcomponents		
	Belt 1	Belt 2	Belt 3		Belt 1	Belt 2	Belt 3
Housing and production means	0.740	0.580	0.507	HHs without a solid house	0.91	0.77	0.705
				HHs with house affected by floods	0.88	0.63	0.595
				HHs without access to production means	0.43	0.34	0.22
Natural Disaster	0.640	0.307	0.325	Average number of flood events in the past 10 years	0.583	0.083	0.167
				HHs with an injury or death as a result of a natural disaster in the last 10 years	0.265	0.125	0.1
				Average number of embankment breaches in the past 10 years	0.75	0.417	0.667
				HHs that do not receive a warning before a natural disaster (flash flood, hailstorm, embankment breach)	0.9	0.81	0.69
				Average number of months that land was water-logged	0.7	0.1	0

Source: calculated by author, 2024

3.2.7. Housing Security and Access to Livelihood Assets

Housing stability and livelihood infrastructure represent critical determinants of vulnerability in flood-prone rural settings. The component Housing Security and Access to Livelihood Assets, as summarized in Table 6, presents the highest vulnerability scores among the analyzed dimensions, 0.740 in Belt 1, 0.580 in Belt 2, and 0.507 in Belt 3, signifying considerable exposure and sensitivity to flood-related hazards in these areas. This component is constituted by three key sub-indicators: the proportion of households without a solid house, households with flood-affected housing, and households lacking access to productive means. Collectively the sub-components indicate a compounded vulnerability where insecure housing and restricted livelihood assets mutually reinforce the adverse impacts of flooding. From both qualitative and quantitative evidence, it is clear that addressing this dimension is critical, not only for reducing immediate flood damage but also for enhancing adaptive capacity and ensuring long-term livelihood security in these ecologically fragile zones.

3.2.8. Disaster Risk Exposure and Vulnerability

The component Disaster Risk Exposure and Vulnerability reflects the degree to which households have historically experienced and continue to face disaster-induced adversities, especially floods. The composite index values show high vulnerability in Belt 1 (0.640), followed by Belt 3 (0.325) and Belt 2 (0.307). A closer look at the sub-components reveals that the average number of flood events over the past decade is significantly higher in Belt 1 (0.583), indicating a recurrent exposure to natural calamities. FGDs confirmed that these communities suffer almost annually from floodwaters, often triggered by heavy monsoons and riverbank overflow. Broadly speaking, the findings make it abundantly evident that homes in regions that experience regular floods; inadequate infrastructure (such as numerous embankment breaches), poor crisis communication, and ongoing water logging continue to be caught in a vicious circle of vulnerability. Their capacity to successfully plan for, respond to, and recover from disasters is hampered by these characteristics taken together. This susceptibility is exacerbated by the lack of institutional early warning mechanisms, as reported in field interviews.

3.3 Comparative Analysis of Major Components of Livelihood Vulnerability across Fringe Belts

To assess and visually compare the multidimensional livelihood vulnerability across the riparian, intermediate, and peripheral belts of Laokhowa-Burhachapori Wildlife Sanctuary, a spider diagram was constructed using the disaggregated scores of major LVI components (Figure 2). The diagram elucidates distinct spatial patterns of vulnerability rooted in socio-economic and environmental exposures.

Notably, riparian belt records heightened vulnerability in housing and production means (0.740) and natural disasters (0.640), underscoring its direct exposure to flooding and inadequate access to resilient infrastructure. This belt’s proximity

Fig 2. Spider diagram comparing the major components of the LVI across the three flood-prone belts

to the core of the sanctuary renders it more susceptible to ecological restrictions and climate-induced hazards, constraining livelihood diversification and access to essential services. The intermediate belt displays relatively balanced vulnerabilities, though it records the highest score in social networks (0.463), reflecting a heavier reliance on communal coping mechanisms, potentially in response to institutional or infrastructural deficits. Meanwhile, the peripheral belt demonstrates comparatively lower vulnerability across most components, with notably reduced scores in livelihood strategy (0.264) and water (0.318), suggesting better diversification of income sources and more secure access to basic utilities.

In comparison to existing literature on flood vulnerability in rural India such as Ghosh and Ghosal in West Bengal⁽¹⁸⁾ and Islam et. al⁽¹⁹⁾ in vulnerabilities caused by tropical flood assessed vulnerability primarily through climatic indicators. Unlike these, this study offers a nuanced, region-specific contribution by integrating spatial proximity to a protected area with household-level livelihood data where flood and erosion vulnerability is compounded by ecological constraints stemming from protected area regulations; a factor rarely integrated into previous LVI frameworks. Additionally, it has used recent primary data (2023) from stratified household surveys and conducts a detailed component-wise breakdown of vulnerability, allowing for localized assessment and comparison across multiple sub-components of exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity. Therefore, the innovation of the present research lies in its context-specific application of the LVI, incorporation of ecological constraints, and its granular, component-wise evaluation that enhances both theoretical understanding and practical policy relevance in disaster-prone conservation-fringe regions. The findings indicate that in addition to environmental factors, governance structures, historical marginalization, and institutional exclusion significantly influence the vulnerability profiles of these communities. This reinforces the argument made by Adger, that vulnerability is not merely a function of exposure but also shaped by systemic socio-political constraints. The study contributes to the growing body of work on disaster vulnerability by introducing a context-sensitive LVI framework that incorporates both quantitative indicators and qualitative insights from local perceptions. This mixed-methods approach advances scientific understanding by revealing hidden patterns of adaptation and resilience specific to riverine environments. For example, the documentation of indigenous coping strategies, such as elevated bamboo housing and collective livestock evacuation, adds to the literature on grassroots adaptation, often overlooked in top-down policy frameworks.

4 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that fringe villages of Assam's riverine wildlife sanctuaries face heightened livelihood vulnerability due to a convergence of high exposure to flood and erosion hazards, socioeconomic sensitivity, and inadequate adaptive capacity. The LVI analysis indicates that Belt 1 shows the greatest vulnerability (LVI = 0.438), with Belt 2 following at 0.374 and Belt 3 at 0.349. The riparian belt demonstrates increased vulnerability, highlighting its direct exposure to flooding and insufficient access to resilient infrastructure. The closeness of this belt to the heart of the sanctuary makes it more vulnerable to environmental constraints and climate-related risks, limiting diversification of livelihoods and access to vital services. By combining geospatial techniques with the LVI framework and qualitatively recording local adaptation tactics such as raised bamboo dwelling and community-based livestock evacuation, the study makes a methodological contribution. These grassroots initiatives, which are frequently disregarded in top-down catastrophe preparation, provide insightful points for resilience frameworks that are

rooted locally. Even though the LVI model may oversimplify complicated dynamics, and the cross-sectional design restricts temporal applicability, the method is nevertheless useful for determining priority areas for intervention.

To sum up, this study contributes to our knowledge of site-specific vulnerability in flood-prone, conservation-restricted settings and offers a solid basis for inclusive, flexible policymaking. Enhancing the resilience of riverine communities under growing hydro-geomorphic stress requires tailored interventions that respect natural restrictions and build local capability.

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6 Contributory Statement

Inku Devi conducted the research and wrote the original manuscript. Dr. Ashok Kumar Bora critically revised the work, supervised the research process, and approved the final version for publication. Both authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

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